

Project acronym: EVERSE
Grant Agreement Number: 101129744
Project full title: European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
Call identifier: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01

General Assembly Meeting report

Author(s):

Aspasia Orfanou	CERTH
Elena Bakoglidou	CERTH
Fotis Psomopoulos	CERTH
Nikos Pechlivanis	CERTH
Patrick Bos	NLeSC
Aleksandra Nenadic	UNIMAN
Shoaib Sufi	UNIMAN
Sanje Fenkart	CERN
Carole Goble	UNIMAN
Daniel Garijo	UPM

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Workshops.....	3
1.1 Aligning EVERSE training efforts to training registries	3
1.2 Indicators review + connection tools/services + dashboard review/assessment	3
1.3 Discussion on the upcoming Policy Brief.....	4
1.4 WP3 - Session dedicated to Tech Watch	5
1.5 Credit/recognition for structured CVs	5
1.6 RSQkit update. Integration with other WPs (3,4,5), feedback & contentathon	6
1.7 Metadata/schemas for research software, connecting/aligning to indicator.....	7
1.8 Identifying EVERSE contributions to the EOSC Macro Roadmap	7
1.9 Training & Engagement. Cohesive vision on the communication strategy	8
2 Work Packages Updates	9
WP1.....	9
WP2.....	9
WP3.....	10
WP4.....	10
WP5.....	11
WP6.....	11
Roadmap.....	13

1 Workshops

1.1 Aligning EVERSE training efforts to training registries

As part of Milestone 15, which focuses on mapping the stocktake of training materials across WP4's research community training initiatives, a structured approach was undertaken to assess existing content and identify gaps. A group exercise was conducted during the parallel session to categorize training materials, followed by a more detailed gap analysis that will be further refined and qualified during a workshop in Q2 2025 in collaboration with WP4. In terms of training registries, several platforms are already available through communities such as the LS RI, ENVRI, PANSOC and SSHOC, with ESCAPE being planned. Specifically, three registries (LS RI, ENVRI, and ESCAPE) are leveraging TeSS as a tool, with the potential to evolve into the OSCARS mTeSS-X infrastructure. Additionally, discussions are ongoing regarding connections with "non-TeSS" infrastructures. Furthermore, efforts are being made to support RSQKit with training content by deploying existing technology to link TeSS, with the need for enhancements to accommodate multiple TeSS instances. A GitHub repository under the EVERSE initiative has also been proposed to manage metadata related to additional training content, which will be integrated and tested through "EVERSE TeSS".

Next actions:

- Detailed categorization of training resources gathered from the MS15 document
- Setup of the ESCAPE TeSS instance and its population with a first set of training resources
- Transfer of the content of the MS15 milestone into a parallel RSQkit structure in the TeSS format as it is referenced in RSQkit and to be integrated into a future EVERSE TeSS instance
- Participation in a workshop organised by WP4 to understand training gaps in the currently collected set of resources.

1.2 Indicators review + connection tools/services + dashboard review/assessment

Name	Definition	Type
Functional Suitability	Represents the degree to which a product or system provides functions that meet stated and implied needs when used under specified conditions	Category
Performance Efficiency	Represents the degree to which a product performs its functions within specified time and throughput parameters and is efficient in the use of resources (such as CPU, memory, storage, network devices, energy, materials...) under specified conditions.	Category
Compatibility	Degree to which a product, system or component can exchange information with other products, systems or components, and/or perform its required functions while sharing the same common environment and resources.	Category
Interaction Capability	Degree to which a product or system can be interacted with by specified users to exchange information via the user interface to complete specific tasks in a variety of contexts of use.	Category
Reliability	Degree to which a system, product or component performs specified functions under specified conditions for a specified period of time	Category
Security	Degree to which a product or system defends against attack patterns by malicious actors and protects information and data so that persons or other products or systems have the degree of data access appropriate to their types and levels of authorization	Category
Maintainability	Represents the degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be modified to improve it, correct it or adapt it to changes in environment, and in requirements	Category
Flexibility	Degree to which a product can be adapted to changes in its requirements, contexts of use or system environment	Category
Safety	Represents the degree to which a product under defined conditions to avoid a state in which human life, health, property, or the environment is endangered	Category

Figure 1: Software Quality Dimensions defined during the GAM workshop.

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1i7tXJCoKFYMQjFa04YQEzmMc2Wdz4jr-vB8o5nOqpAw/edit?gid=0#gid=0>

In this session a discussion was held to define key terms, focusing on indicators and dimensions, alongside a broader conversation on the role of indicators. It was agreed to begin with existing ISO indicators while incorporating elements of sustainability, FAIRness, and maintainability. Additionally, it was decided to integrate existing indicators, even in cases where some ambiguity exists. Efforts will also be made to align these indicators with relevant schemas.

Next actions:

- Create a first version of the indicator catalog, including the three or four indicators and the eleven dimensions agreed on in the GA meeting.
- Hackathon to test the indicators and relationship with tools. In particular, indicators from three different tools for code quality.

1.3 Discussion on the upcoming Policy Brief

The EVERSE project aims to establish a common European knowledge base for best practices in research software, driven by community engagement and evidenced by RSQKit. To ensure sustainability, mechanisms for funding, support, and continuous updates must be implemented, keeping pace with emerging advancements. It is essential to adopt a shared definition of research software quality, along with recognized indicators across domains, to maintain and build upon past investments while addressing security, code mobility, and green computing challenges. Recognizing and rewarding contributions in research software is crucial for formalizing the role of Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and supporting capacity-building efforts to professionalize the field. In addition, strengthening community-building efforts and bridging diverse groups such as researchers who code, RSE societies, and initiatives like Carpentries/ReSA will further reinforce collaboration. Ultimately, EVERSE seeks to leverage Europe's research software capacity to develop a resilient, independent, and strategically valuable ecosystem, fostering diversity while encouraging convergence to maximize investment and global competitiveness. ReSA is forming some new stakeholder forums, and one of these may be focused on national policymakers aiming for outputs such as an audit of national policies that already embrace research software and/or identification of policy elements that governments could utilise (recognising that many countries can benefit from simply adding some research software policy elements to their existing open science/research policy).

A useful example is ORFG's Open Scholarship Policy Clause Bank, designed to make policy development as easy as possible for funders. It includes sample language for policies covering a range of different scholarly outputs and sharing practices. Funders can identify the plug-and-play language that best fits their needs

As such, the key points to be added to the 1st Policy Brief of EVERSE are the following:

1. We need to have a common European knowledge base for good practices on research software driven by the communities
2. We need to adopt a common definition of research software quality, building on the common perception of research software quality and its indicators across domains.
3. Recognize and reward contributions in research software in order to build towards a formal accreditation of the RSE professional.
4. We need to support capacity-building activities in order to consolidate the professionalism of the European practitioners in the research software field.
5. Capitalize on the research software capacities within Europe and develop a resilient, robust and independent research software ecosystem and recognize its value as a European asset

Next actions:

- By M15 (June 2025), CERTH to put together a first draft of the policy brief, based on the key points that were discussed and identified in the workshop

1.4 WP3 - Session dedicated to Tech Watch

The goal of the EVERSE Tech Watch process is to ensure accurate tracking and evaluation of research software tools. The current [tool](#) placement within Tech Watch, based on the collected tools sheet from D3.1, requires review to improve metadata mapping. A collaborative exercise on the MIRO board was conducted to define a structured process for maintaining and upgrading tools. Moving forward, key next steps include finalizing the process for adding and nominating new tools via GitHub issues, establishing a dedicated curation team to review and merge submissions, and upgrading the tech watch dashboard based on feedback from the GAM workshop. Additionally, improvements will focus on enhancing tool search through metadata and indicators, integrating Tech Watch with RSQKit, and defining milestones potentially by August 25 to finalize the process and refine dashboards.

1.5 Credit/recognition for structured CVs

The action plan for credit and recognition builds upon Deliverable D5.1, aiming to establish a clear mechanism for acknowledging research software contributions. In the short term, efforts are focused on achieving Milestone 16 (MS16) by August 2025, developing a proof of concept for a recognition system that can be easily integrated into CVs. This prototype will be tested by engaging trainers and research software engineers, with the OSCARS/EVERSE school in January 2026 considered as a potential pilot case. The long-term objective is to outline a comprehensive action plan for Task 5.2 until the project's completion. Ongoing work on the MIRO board needs to be aligned with a concept driven by the APICURON team and refined in accordance with the proposal and deliverable requirements. This alignment will also include strong interactions between APICURON, BIP!Scholar, and OpenEBench, to improve interoperability. Key next steps include hosting a series of dedicated online workshops, particularly aimed at defining technical details for the proof of concept and exploring how to align metric indicators to make them measurable. A dedicated regular meeting will also be set up to track progress towards MS16. Further, discussions around the credit and recognition framework should explore the gaps and challenges identified in D5.1, with an emphasis on turning these insights into concrete actionable steps for the implementation of the framework.

Next actions:

- Setup of a regular (bi-weekly) meeting of stakeholders of the credit and recognition framework to track progress of the implementation towards the MS16 milestone
- Participation in a workshop organised by WP4 to gather feedback on useful metrics to be implemented for the prototype of the recognition framework

1.6 RSQKit update. Integration with other WPs (3,4,5), feedback & contentation

Figure 2: Internal links between RSQKit and related EVERSE tasks and work packages.

Figure 3: List of responses collected during the workshop via Slido poll.

In this workshop, numerous RSQKit's connection points were highlighted with various work packages and tasks, emphasizing the importance of integration and co-design. There was unanimous support for Research Stories, focusing on clusters, infrastructure, and software, with a clear understanding that the needs for indicators and dimensions are centered on people, not machines – hence we urgently need a practical model for software quality indicators and dimensions that can be utilised immediately to curate resources in RSQKit (tools, tasks, and other resources) while the technical aspects of the model are being finalised by WP2 Task 2.3. A demo and feedback session were held to help prioritize tasks, including discussions on task naming, followed by a contentation. The EVERSE project is guided by the goals of what people want to achieve, rather than just the product itself like balancing identifiers with getting software publication-ready. A discussion related to technical

development of the RSQKit followed with a focus on SEO, sustainability, and policy challenges. Efforts to make contributing easier, even for non-technical users or those without GitHub experience, were discussed. The editorial board needs to expand and include new members that will encompass more communities within EVERSE, such as ESCAPE, Tools & radar representation. Monthly updates for RSQKit are planned, and a timeline revision will be based on feedback from the recent session. The D3.2 tools deliverable, due by the end of August, aims to integrate RSQKit with indicators and dimensions, which would be a major milestone.

Next actions:

- Update the research software lifecycle diagram and link it to content in RSQKit
- Update the 3-tier view of software (abundance/importance aspect) and link it to content in RSQKit
- Research communities, clusters, infrastructures and stories – definitions in RSQKit need clarifying and some renaming needs to happen
- Templates for research communities, research software stories and roles need updating or creating
- RS Quality - need a high-level list of dimensions and links to indicators
- Profiles – linked to roles and tasks and competency levels

1.7 Metadata/schemas for research software, connecting/aligning to indicator

In the first *metadata schemas* part, three schemas were presented: Dimensions, Indicators, and Software Quality (SQ) tools, all of which feature persistent URLs. It was also noted that persistent identifiers could be created for tool entries. The SQ-Tools metadata schema builds on existing metadata (CodeMeta), with four additional attributes. Minor adjustments were suggested, which are now available as issues. The emphasis was placed on simplicity, as overcomplicating the schema could make it challenging to add all necessary data for each tool. In the second part, *Assessment metadata* an interactive session was conducted to gather feedback. Again, the goal was to keep it simple, with essential elements like links to the pipeline, status, and date. Dimensions were considered unnecessary for the current stage. Short-term plans include identifying an example tool, determining the indicators it can provide, and developing a demo pipeline for further feedback

Next actions:

- Update the indicators schema to v0.0.2 to accommodate indicator metadata agreed on in the GAM.
- Validation pipelines to comply with the schemas defined in EVERSE.
- Create the first agreed version of the assessment schema.
- Create examples using the assessment schema with indicators, integrated with quality pipelines in EVERSE.

1.8 Identifying EVERSE contributions to the EOSC Macro Roadmap

The main goal of the workshop was to review and update the EVERSE entries under the EOSC Macro Roadmap (<https://eosc.eu/eosc-macro-roadmap/>). Specifically, the rewards and recognition framework for software/data stewards will be redefined as the credit and recognition framework for research software-related activities. The Research Software Quality toolkit is central to this initiative, which is aligned with the transition of the EVERSE network to a cross-domain network focused on the theme of Research Software Quality. Additionally, the FAIR assessment dashboard, previously aimed at monitoring research software quality, will now be redefined as a reference model of research software quality indicators and their

dimensions. Furthermore, a new resource, an atlas of Research Software Quality, will be introduced to provide comprehensive information on research software quality resources.

In shorthand:

- Credit and recognition framework for research software-related activities (to replace the currently listed *Rewards and recognition framework for software/data stewards*)
- Research Software Quality Toolkit (remains as is)
- EVERSE Network focused on the theme of Research Software Quality (to replace the currently listed *EVERSE Network*)
- A reference model of research software quality indicators and their dimensions (to replace the currently listed *FAIR Assessment Dashboard to monitor research software quality*)
- An Atlas of Research Software Quality resources (to be added)

Next actions:

- CERTH to communicate these changes to EOSC-A, in order for the EVERSE entries to be updated.

1.9 Training & Engagement. Cohesive vision on the communication strategy

The goal is to gather input from various individuals and science clusters (including pilots) on how EVERSE is engaging and should engage with scientific communities and stakeholders. This includes both interim results and training aspects. Based on the collected [input](#) as well as using a “revision and outlook” tool on Miroboards, plans for future events and activities were made. Referring to training, tasks that will be undertaken in WP5:

- Develop TeSS with the inputs in the “longed for” category.
- Map trainers and their competencies within the EVERSE consortium (and consider creating training working groups).
- Define clear training objectives and establish a central repository for training materials.

For the engagement, what needs to be discussed further is the agreement upon and the understanding of effective engagement of KPIs. In addition, it needs to be defined how to onboard people who are volunteering to work in EVERSE working groups. For the engagement, the tasks that will be covered in WP1 and WP4 are the following:

- Identify the EOSC “groups” and funded projects to engage with
- Revise elevator pitch
- Keep a “conference tracker” a common “abstract/slides” repo Keep engaging with Network members (mailing list, Mattermost, etc.)
- Provide platform to present (Network webinars)
- EVERSE calendar (with webinars for the outside)

Next actions:

- Stand up EVERSE TeSS instance as a registry of training resources on RS quality collected by EVERSE – an interim step before mTeSS-X multi tenanted instance is developed
- Continue collecting, curating, and refining training resources collected as part of “MS15 - Mapping of the stocktake of training materials across the training initiatives in the research communities of WP4 and a first assessment on gaps to be filled.”

2 Work Packages Updates

WP1

In the process of establishing a European Network of Research Software Quality EVERSE has actively engaged with numerous communities and initiatives. Engagements have included a poster and lightning talk at RSECon; and a significant presence with a poster at deRSE, a RSQkit contentathon, and skill-up session focused on Software Research Lifecycles. EVERSE also reached out to specific scientific communities such as those involved with GANIL and the Einstein Telescope, as well as the SKA SRCNet community. The project presented its work at the HSF/WLCG Workshop and contributed to the ELIXIR European Biohackathon and ENVRI-HUB project meetings. Furthermore, it has supported the ELIXIR STEERS project, which aims to improve software management practices across 23 countries.

Broader engagement continued through participation in the OSCARS General Assembly, which included funded open call projects, as well as networking with the OpenAIRE NOAD network. EVERSE showcased its initiatives with a poster at the 3rd Symposium for Open Science and collaborated with initiatives such as SciCodes, CodeMeta, Workflow Community Initiative, the RSI forum, and CZI hackathons. Communication efforts have expanded through the EVERSE website, social media, and the “Into the EVERSE” newsletter, helping increase outreach and visibility.

A significant milestone was the EVERSE Network Launch Event, which had high participation and positive engagement. Looking ahead, there is active planning of webinars, skill-up sessions, and international events, including one in Africa targeting policymakers and global RS stakeholders. In addition, EVERSE’s future planning includes key milestones: onboarding new scientific communities (D1.1, ELIXIR, Apr 2025), establishing joint activities with industry partners (MS2, UEDIN, Aug 2025), and expanding community engagement (D1.2, ELIXIR, Feb 2026). A roadmap for a permanent virtual institute (MS3, CERN, Aug 2026) and a fully active European research software network (D1.3, CERN, Feb 2027) are also in progress. As WP1 remains a key hub for EVERSE’s collaborative and training activities, it relies on community input to ensure effective and inclusive communication.

WP2

Since the project started, WP2 has made significant progress in collection of best practices for the development of high-quality research software. More specifically, in Task 2.1, a landscape survey launched in July–August 2024 has been gathering insights on best practices across clusters and individuals, with ongoing analysis to identify shared practices, gaps, and priorities. Task 2.2 has led to the successful setup and initial implementation of the RSQkit, including the editorial process, structure, and its first release on 18 February 2024 (Milestone 5). Meanwhile, in Task 2.3 there are discussions with WP3 on indicators and metadata schemas to guide software quality, FAIRness, and maturity. Particular care will need to be given to ensure that there is a balance between practical indicators (i.e. indicators that developers can actually use to help themselves) and automated indicators (i.e. indicators that can be effectively use to assess quality on a scale, but are unlikely to be used in practice by a developer).

In the coming months, by September 2025, WP2 will build upon these foundations by presenting survey results at an April webinar, launching follow-up surveys tailored to EVERSE implementations, and enriching RSQkit with new content and templates. Integration with WP3 will support tool-based annotations, and the editorial board will be expanded to better reflect community diversity. Guidelines for the first indicator set will be created and tested in WP4 pilots. By March 2026, WP2 aims to refine these guidelines based on pilot feedback,

standardize them further, and ensure their integration into dashboards and pipelines. Follow-up surveys and comprehensive RSQkit content updates will reflect evolving best practices, with strategic input from the EVERSE network and WP3's Radar system.

Key milestones already achieved include the initial landscaping report (MS4), the RSQkit release (MS5), and the deliverable of initial aspect collections for software quality (D2.1). Upcoming deliverables include the Mid-term Report (D2.2) and the initial list of indicators (MS6). Outreach efforts are well underway, with planned webinars across all WP2 tasks during the EVERSE Network series, including events on 15 April and May 2025.

WP3

WP3 is advancing a coordinated approach to software quality within the EOSC ecosystem through its three core tasks. Task 3.1 Technology Watch has compiled a comprehensive catalogue of 77 tools and services designed to improve software quality and FAIRness. These tools are organized according to dimensions such as Sustainability and Openness. This catalogue, submitted as Deliverable D3.1 (December 2024), was evaluated during a dedicated workshop (Milestone 8, February 2025) and is currently being integrated into RSQKit and TechRadar using standardized metadata schemas. The upcoming phase will focus on curating the catalogue further, linking tools to specific quality indicators (Deliverable D3.2), and ensuring long-term sustainability in collaboration with Task Force 1. Of particular note in this context is the published work on “Applying the FAIR Principles to computational workflows” (Sci Data12, 328, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04451-9>) that was produced in partnership with the Workflow Community Initiative.

Building on this foundation, Task 3.2 Integrated Pipelines is developing automated, containerized workflows that assess and enhance software quality. These pipelines aim to enrich metadata, support FAIR compliance, and streamline the integration of quality assurance into the development process.

Meanwhile, Task 3.3 Dashboards has delivered a functional prototype that includes a complete system design, an ORM model, a synthetic data generator, and a containerized testing setup. While the dashboard is technically operational, further refinement of the user interface is still needed. Over the next six months, efforts will concentrate on automating deployment via Kubernetes, integrating with cloud services, synchronizing schemas, and improving documentation and branding. Within twelve months, the system will incorporate real data from the pipelines and provide tailored views for different stakeholders and researchers. Looking further ahead, user feedback will guide continuous improvements, and outreach will be supported through a blog post or software paper (Milestone 10, Month 24).

WP4

Since the beginning of the project, WP4 has focused on documenting the initial landscape of the science cluster pilots, including recording presentations that captured the existing state of the art practises. These recordings, which include indicators and training insights from early drafts of the Reference Model, are planned to be converted into webinars for dissemination via WP1 on the website and Zenodo. WP4 also contributed to technology monitoring through the Miro board and supported various questionnaires. Currently, pilot leads are drafting user story pages for RSQKit. These efforts have fed into Deliverable D4.1 and highlighted key findings. Among the main challenges are ensuring sustainability in the context of short-term contributors, balancing accessibility with advanced feature development, and maintaining consistency in metrics versus domain-specific needs. However, several strengths were also identified: all pilots are already under version control, and strong onboarding and community-building practices are in place. In the next six months, EVERSE enters a phase that must prove its value to research software users, with initial releases of RSQKit, training resources, tools,

and metrics. These should be validated through the pilot projects to ensure they are easy to use, useful, and complete. Pilots are expected to take a more active role, ultimately becoming champions of best practices. To achieve this, RSQKit user stories are being developed to clarify benefits, and pilot leads are being embedded across task forces and work packages to support adoption. Engagement and assessment procedures are being prototyped (D4.2/4.3), supported by joint hackathons with WP2 and ongoing feedback across WPs.

Looking ahead to the next 12 months, the focus shifts to implementing, testing, and measuring good practices, allowing time for iterative development and feedback loops. Activities will be prioritized into achievable steps starting with version control and moving toward deeper evaluations to gradually make EVERSE's impact visible. WP4 is advancing key milestones and deliverables, including feedback on shared software quality metrics (MS12, 8/2025) and training materials from pilot courses (MS13, 2/2026), alongside deliverables D4.2 and D4.3 on software assessment for researchers. Related outputs such as onboarding (D1.1), RSQKit tools (D3.2), training resources (D5.2), and indicator frameworks (MS9, MS10) support pilot integration. Outreach plans include a joint hackathon with WP2 to refine indicators, conference contributions (e.g., ESCAPE 2025), and community-driven activities like "Improve your code" hackathons and OSCARS platform presentations.

WP5

WP5: Capacity Building and Recognition focuses on consolidating and recognizing training efforts within the EVERSE initiative. The work package has begun collecting training resources to address the needs of WP4 use cases and RSQKit tasks. Milestone 15, submitted in February 2025, outlines a mapping of existing training materials and identifies gaps, supported by a survey revealing strong awareness of FAIR and RSE resources but limited outreach beyond EOSC clusters. The recognition framework leverages tools such as APICURON and Bip! Scholar, aiming to connect with broader platforms like ORCID. Deliverable 5.1, submitted in February 2024, analyzed existing reward mechanisms and highlighted a list of promising initiatives aligned with fair, transparent, and inclusive practices. Long-term sustainability is addressed through proposed events targeting students and early-career researchers, built upon RSQKit content, and through the creation of a network of trainers leveraging existing training networks. As a key next step, the OSCARS / EVERSE School will take place from 21 – 28 January 2026 in Annecy, France, focusing on best practices through a hands-on topic and aiming to produce a paper from the school's results. The training effort will leverage WP5 resources and recognize contributions from trainers spanning EOSC science clusters.

The architecture for recognition is being developed using tools like APICURON and Bip!Scholar, with Milestone 16 defining CV-ready recognition mechanisms (UNIPD, M18) and Deliverable 5.4 outlining a full recognition framework (CERN, M36). A seminar series and network of trainers are being established to highlight tools and best practices, with coordination via WP1 and WP4 to address training gaps. Training catalogues are being integrated through TeSS instances across EOSC clusters, potentially unified under the OSCARS mTeSS-X project, with Milestone 17 delivering a prototype training catalogue (CNRS, M24). In parallel, RSQKit-linked training resources are being curated and refined through Deliverables 5.2 and 5.3 (UPM, M18 and M32), ensuring alignment with software best practices and community feedback.

WP6

Since the beginning of the project, significant progress has been made under Work Package 6 (WP6). The Grant Agreement was approved in October 2023, marking the official start of the project. This was followed by the organization of the Kick-off Meeting in March 2024, which laid the groundwork for collaborative efforts. The Consortium Agreement was approved in

September 2024, further solidifying partnerships. Pre-financing arrangements were finalized in November 2024, ensuring financial readiness for implementation. A key milestone was the signing of the Memorandum of Understanding between FAIRCORE4EOSC and EVERSE in October 2024, reinforcing strategic collaboration. In terms of outputs, Deliverables D6.1, D6.2, and D6.3 were all submitted on time. Additionally, activities related to Artificial Intelligence within EVERSE and various outreach events were initiated to foster engagement and visibility. In the next six months, WP6 will concentrate on key actions leading up to the submission of the 1st Periodic Report. As part of the preparation process, an initial email will be sent to the finance mailing list by 25 August 2025, outlining specific guidelines and deadlines for input. This will be followed by the collection of partner contributions, with feedback from all consortium members expected by 30 September 2025. The final report will then be consolidated and submitted through the EU Portal by 30 October 2025. These steps are essential to ensure readiness for the EC Mid-Term Review and to maintain alignment with the overall project timeline.

Roadmap

The 1st EVERSE General Assembly Meeting wrapped up with a discussion on the next steps, both looking within the project as well as towards the overarching theme of the project in the context of the broader ecosystem.

The discussion on the internal roadmap discussions emphasized the need for clearer integration and shared understanding across work packages (WPs). To strengthen RSQKit's editorial board, increased engagement from other WPs is encouraged, with tasks expected to be delegated from upcoming editorial board meetings. While the long-term plan is to focus on content development within a year, there will be efforts in monthly sprints with feedback at each sprint's conclusion. A six-month review of RSQKit's progress was suggested to ensure alignment.

The Reference Model document should serve as a foundational guide for all WPs, helping them align their contributions within a shared theoretical framework that can continue beyond the lifespan of the EVERSE project. While RSQKit provides practical recipes, the Reference Framework offers a more abstract conceptual layer, both aimed at creating coherence across diverse initiatives. Task forces (TFs) play a key role in fostering this shared understanding, especially TF2, which requires clearer definitions and dimensions to function effectively. Pilot cases from Life Sciences and projects like ESCAPE, EVRI-Hub, PANOSC, and SSHOC will serve as testbeds for RSQKit applications. Looking ahead to the second year, integration between components, especially RSQKit and the editorial board, will be crucial, alongside coordinated training and the establishment of shared vocabularies, glossaries, and legal frameworks for the EVERSE Virtual Institute. While TFs operate with minimal structure, using platforms like Mattermost rather than scheduled meetings, they remain open to participation from external collaborators interested in the EVERSE project.

Key action:

1. By M18 (ideally by M15/June 2025), demonstrate compatibility/alignment across the various EVERSE outputs (such as the RSQkit, Dashboard, Atlas, the Network, etc.) through either soft or hard links across services.

Looking beyond EVERSE, the main discussion focused on the sustainability element of EVERSE. There are three main directions: (a) pursue the concept of connecting to the wider EOSC Ecosystem with EVERSE as a thematic EOSC Node, (b) pursue the concept of establishing an independent entity (i.e., the Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence), and (c) focus primarily on identifying additional strands of funding that will support EVERSE after the end of the project lifecycle. The first option relies heavily on the expected structure and requirement of an EOSC Node, neither of which are clear at this stage – however, some clarity is expected closer to the end of 2025 (i.e. around the middle of the project). The 2nd option requires already some effort on identifying the possible regulatory and legal frameworks that this entity might fall under, and the 3rd option is very risky, and publicly available funding is generally difficult to obtain.

Key action:

1. By M23 (ideally by M18), produce a business canvas of the various EVERSE outputs, in order to identify the possible sustainability options.